

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Case Study

Metoprolol-Induced Syncope and Nicoumalone-Induced Bruising: A Case Report of Dose-Dependent Adverse Drug Reactions.

Rengaraj Thirunanamoorthy¹, Thaslim Ridhwana Barakath Ali², Pari Kumanan^{*3},
Surya Rajendran⁴, Vennila Sankar⁵

¹ Department of General Medicine, Government Medical College and Hospital, Nagapattinam, Tamil Nadu, India.

^{2,3,4,5} Department of Pharmacy Practice, EGS Pillay College of Pharmacy, Nagapattinam..

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 17 Oct 2025

Keywords:

Metoprolol, Syncope,
Hypotension, Nicoumalone,
Bruising, Case Report.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17379793

ABSTRACT

This case report documents the adverse drug reactions experienced by a 40-year-old female with rheumatic heart disease and severe mitral regurgitation after percutaneous transvenous mitral commissurotomy, admitted with syncope and atrial fibrillation with rapid ventricular response. She was treated with anticoagulants, antiplatelets, and metoprolol. Subsequently, she developed probable dose-related syncope from metoprolol-induced hypotension and spontaneous bruising due to nicoumalone-associated bruising, confirmed by elevated INR. Both adverse drug reactions were assessed using the Naranjo scale and deemed probable. Management involved reducing the dose of metoprolol and nicoumalone. It also involved switching from Clopidogrel to low-dose aspirin, with clinical improvement. This case points out the critical importance of careful drug titration, vigilant monitoring of anticoagulation, and early recognition of adverse reactions in patients with valvular heart disease and atrial fibrillation. It highlights the vital role of interdisciplinary collaboration, including that of clinical pharmacists, in optimizing therapy and minimizing risks associated with polypharmacy in critical care settings.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatic heart disease (RHD) remains a significant cause of cardiovascular morbidity in

developing nations, often leading to valvular dysfunction such as mitral regurgitation and stenosis. Despite declining prevalence in high-income countries, RHD continues to affect

***Corresponding Author:** Pari Kumanan

Address: Department of Pharmacy Practice, EGS Pillay College of Pharmacy, Nagapattinam.

Email ✉: parikumanan2001@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

millions globally from low- and middle-income regions, particularly young and female adults [1, 2]. Percutaneous transvenous mitral commissurotomy (PTMC) is a widely adopted minimally invasive intervention for relief of mitral stenosis, with favorable hemodynamic and survival benefits [3].

Patients with RHD and atrial fibrillation (AF) are frequently associated with one another. This combination, especially in the post-PTMC period, requires long-term anticoagulation and often concomitant antiplatelet therapy to prevent thromboembolic events. However, polypharmacy in such patients increases the risk of adverse drug reactions (ADRs), which may be severe or life-threatening.

Nicoumalone, being a vitamin K antagonist, potentially can reduce the synthesis of clotting factors II, VII, IX, and X, thereby increasing the risk of bleeding and bruising [4]. Similarly, beta-blockers like metoprolol are frequently used for rate control in AF but can cause dose-dependent hypotension and bradyarrhythmia [5].

Early recognition, assessment, and management of ADRs in patients with complex cardiovascular disease are integral to optimizing therapy and preventing complications in critical care settings.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 40-year-old female with a known history of rheumatic heart disease (RHD) and severe mitral regurgitation, status post percutaneous transvenous mitral commissurotomy (PTMC), was admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) with complaints of giddiness, syncope, and pain over the lower lip, which was suspected to be trauma-induced from a syncopal episode.

On initial examination, the patient was hemodynamically stable, with a blood pressure

(BP) of 110/70 mmHg and a pulse rate of 104 bpm. Capillary blood glucose was 94 mg/dL. Laboratory investigations revealed thrombocytopenia (platelet count: 84,000/ μ L) and a normal international normalized ratio (INR) of 1.17. ECG showed atrial fibrillation (AF) with a rapid ventricular response (RVR).

Management was initiated with subcutaneous heparin, oral Acitrom (nicoumalone) 4 mg once daily, and Tab. Metoprolol 250 mg twice daily for rate control. The patient was also started on Tab. Clopidogrel 150 mg once daily, Tab. Atorvastatin 40 mg, penicillin prophylaxis, and supportive medications.

Over the next three days, the patient remained clinically stable. However, on Day 4, she experienced another episode of syncope, with a documented drop in BP to 90/60 mmHg. In view of the temporal relationship between high-dose metoprolol administration and the onset of hypotension and syncope, a dose-related adverse drug reaction (ADR) was suspected. Tab. Metoprolol was dose-adjusted to 100 mg twice daily, after which no further syncopal episodes were reported.

Additionally, the patient began to report spontaneous bruising over the extremities. Repeat laboratory evaluation revealed a significant increase in INR to 3.3, while platelet count remained low. In light of the elevated INR, low platelets, and bruising, Nicoumalone-induced bleeding was suspected. The dose of Tab. Nicoumalone was also reduced to 2mg, and additionally, Clopidogrel was discontinued, and low-dose aspirin (75 mg) was introduced as an alternative antiplatelet agent. The patient's bruising subsequently stabilized, and no major bleeding events were observed.

The suspected ADRs were assessed using the Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale:

- Syncope due to Metoprolol: Probable (score 6)
- Easy bruising due to Nicoumalone: Possible (score 3)

This case highlights the importance of individualized drug titration and close monitoring of anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapy in patients with atrial fibrillation and valvular heart disease, especially those with baseline thrombocytopenia. It also emphasizes the need for early recognition of ADRs, particularly in the critical care setting, where polypharmacy is common.

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates two probable adverse drug reactions in a patient with rheumatic heart disease (RHD), atrial fibrillation (AF), and baseline thrombocytopenia. The first event, syncope associated with high-dose metoprolol, was likely due to excessive beta-blockade leading to hypotension. In AF cases with rapid ventricular response, the primary treatment strategy is to reduce heart rate; beta blockers such as metoprolol are recommended to slow the ventricular heart rate [4]. Beta-blockers, particularly at higher doses, can precipitate bradycardia, hypotension, and syncope, especially in patients with structural heart disease and limited cardiac reserve [5]. In this case, the patient fainted on day 4, the vital examination showed a drop in the blood pressure to 90/60mmHg. Careful dose titration is essential to balance rate control with hemodynamic stability.

Though clopidogrel, acitrom, and heparin act on different pathways, their primary aim is to prevent clots. Clopidogrel inhibits platelet activation by blocking ADP receptors on platelets, preventing aggregation. Coumarin anticoagulants inhibit vitamin K epoxide reductase, reducing the synthesis of clotting factors. Heparin enhances antithrombin III activity, which inactivates thrombin and factor Xa, preventing fibrin formation [6, 7, 8]

The second event, easy bruising and elevated INR while on clopidogrel, nicoumalone, and heparin, underscores the bleeding risks of triple antithrombotic therapy, especially in thrombocytopenic patients. Polypharmacy with anticoagulants and antiplatelets markedly increases bleeding risk, a concern supported by large clinical trials and observational data [5]. The synergy between platelet inhibition and anticoagulation can undermine hemostasis even in the absence of trauma.

Approximately double the risk is noticed in the patients when the INR gets above 3.0. Since Nicoumalone can increase the INR, the patient must be monitored carefully to prevent bleeding risks. The risk of bleeding doubles for each one-point increase. [9]

The role of the Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale was crucial in objectifying causality assessment, aiding clinical decision-making [10]. Early identification and prompt modification of therapy by reducing the metoprolol dose and modifying antithrombotic therapy led to the resolution of symptoms without further complications.

Table 1: Naranjo ADR Probability Assessment Scale

Naranjo Algorithm Question	Syncope due to Metoprolol	Easy Bruising due to Nicoumalone
1. Are there previous conclusive reports on this reaction?	+1	+1

2. Did the adverse event appear after the suspected drug was given?	+2	+2
3. Did the adverse reaction improve when the drug was discontinued or a specific antagonist was given?	+1(dose reduction)	+1(discontinuation)
4. Did the adverse reaction reappear when the drug was readministered?	0	0
5. Are there alternative causes that could on their own have caused the reaction?	+2	-1 (Presence of other anticoagulant and antiplatelet drugs)
6. Did the reaction reappear when a placebo was given?	0	0
7. Was the drug detected in blood (or other fluids) in concentrations known to be toxic?	0	0
8. Was the reaction more severe when the dose was increased or less severe when the dose was decreased?	+1	0
9. Did the patient have a similar reaction to the same or similar drugs in any previous exposure?	0	0
10. Was the adverse event confirmed by any objective evidence?	+1 (hypotension documented)	+1(elevated INR, bruising)

This case emphasizes that in RHD patients with AF, individualized pharmacologic regimens, vigilant monitoring of INR and platelet counts, and early recognition of ADRs are vital for optimal outcomes, particularly in the critical care setting where drug interactions and cumulative effects are common.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the essential role of individualized pharmacotherapy and meticulous monitoring in managing patients with rheumatic heart disease and atrial fibrillation receiving complex anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapies. The identification and management of dose-related adverse drug reactions, such as metoprolol-induced syncope and clopidogrel-associated bleeding, demonstrate the critical importance of interdisciplinary collaboration. Clinical pharmacists play an indispensable role in optimizing drug regimens, detecting potential drug-drug interactions, and educating healthcare teams on adverse effect management. Their involvement is pivotal in enhancing patient safety,

minimizing adverse drug events, and improving therapeutic outcomes, particularly in high-risk and polypharmacy settings like critical care. This case reinforces the need for a proactive pharmacovigilance approach to ensure safe and effective cardiovascular care.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all those who have supported me throughout the course of this work. I am deeply thankful for the guidance and encouragement I have received from my mentors, family, and friends. I also extend my appreciation to the physicians, nurses, and other healthcare professionals who contributed to the diagnosis and care of the individuals involved in this study.

DECLARATIONS

Funding: No funding sources

Conflict of interest: None declared

Ethical approval: Not required

REFERENCES

1. Zühlke L, Engel ME, Karthikeyan G, Rangarajan S, Mackie P, Cupido B, et al. Characteristics, complications, and gaps in evidence-based interventions in rheumatic heart disease: the Global Rheumatic Heart Disease Registry (the REMEDY study). *Eur Heart J*. 2015;36:1115–1122
2. Watkins DA, Johnson CO, Colquhoun SM, Karthikeyan G, Beaton A, Bukhman G, et al. Global, regional, and national burden of rheumatic heart disease, 1990–2015. *N Engl J Med*. 2017;377:713–722
3. Vahanian A, Palacios IF. Percutaneous approaches to valvular disease. *Clin Cardiol*. 2004;27:1572–1579.
4. Burum A, Carino J, McBeth M, Samuel N, Hintze TD. A systematic review of weight-based metoprolol for acute atrial fibrillation with rapid ventricular rate. *Emerg Med Int*. 2023;2023:3138064. doi:10.1155/2023/3138064
5. Pirmohamed M, James S, Meakin S, Green C, Scott AK, Walley TJ, et al. Adverse drug reactions as cause of admission to hospital: prospective analysis of 18,820 patients. *BMJ*. 2004;329:15–19.
6. Cattaneo M. Aspirin and clopidogrel: efficacy, safety, and the issue of drug resistance. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol*. 2004;24:1980–1987.
7. Shakthivel CD, Murugesan J. Rare case report on Acitrom induced coagulopathy with seizure disorder. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2025 Aug;13(8):3516–3521.
8. Patel P, Huang D. Heparin. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK538247/>
9. Dentali F, Ageno W. Management of coumarin-associated coagulopathy in the non-bleeding patient: a systematic review. *Haematologica*. 2004 Jul;89(7):857–862. PMID: 15257939.
10. Naranjo CA, Busto U, Sellers EM, Sandor P, Ruiz I, Roberts EA, et al. A method for estimating the probability of adverse drug reactions. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 1981;30(2):239–245.

HOW TO CITE: Rengaraj Thirunanamoorthy, Thaslim Ridhwana Barakath Ali, Pari Kumanan, Surya Rajendran, Vennila Sankar, Metoprolol-Induced Syncope and Nicoumalone-Induced Bruising: A Case Report of Dose-Dependent Adverse Drug Reactions, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 10, 1908-1912. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17379793>

